

VICTOR SLAVESCU'S INVOLVEMENT IN SUPPORTING THE LAND LOAN BETWEEN 1920 AND 1944

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Abstract

Victor Slavescu was and will remain a personality with special academic, legislative and applied contributions at the level of public, financial-banking and academic institutions, being in permanent contact with all systemic problems of the country. Moreover, following studies conducted abroad, he was part of the generation of specialists in the country, from which he expected both a direct scientific contribution, but especially a direct involvement in the implementation of reforms in the period 1920–1944.

In this paper we aim to reflect the contributions and involvement of Victor Slavescu in supporting land loans between 1920 and 1944, contributions that can be extremely beneficial in the sustainable development of the mountain economy, especially in the context in which two major concepts are currently reflected economic development, namely the collaborative economy and the green economy, and land credit as defined at that time can be a real source of inspiration for current generations of financiers involved in supporting and developing credit for sustainable rural development.

Keywords: *rural financing, mountain economy and sustainability.*

JEL classification code: *Q14, Q10, Q56.*

INTRODUCTION

Victor Slavescu, through his way of thinking, was convinced that one of the main problems to be solved was that of the peasants, of Romanian agriculture in general, as evidenced by the topic of the doctoral thesis (Slavescu, 1907). In many of his studies he used to mention an old German proverb, in which he strongly believed: "Hat der Bauer Geld, hat die ganze Welt" (If the peasant has money, everyone has it). Even though the decree for the implementation of the agrarian reform was issued in 1919 and the law was adopted in 1921, the situation in the territory was much more complicated. For each of the Romanian provinces a special law had to be adopted, which would be adapted to the specific existing conditions. The division of the land was difficult; a lot consisted of an average of 3.8 ha, which was insufficient to solve the problems faced by the peasantry (specialists' calculations showed that an economically independent household had to own at least 5 ha) (Scurtu, 1996:12). The ownership was made by compensation, and for the work of the lands with which they were put in possession, the peasants needed an agricultural inventory which they did not have and which they could only buy on credit.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

To support research methodology, classical observational and examination tools, and research methods based on the basic principles of scientific research, namely: competence,

objectivity, truth, methodology, demonstration, correlation, evaluation of results, usefulness and psychomotor (Ristea and Franc, 2013). It will use procedures based on factual analysis, intensive documentation at the level of domestic and international literature, using existing databases and scientific material in the endowment of libraries of specific institutes in Romania and internationally. The methodology of the paper has as direct tools the collection of data and information from literature and existing practice in public and private institutions, but especially scientific articles published on specialized research networks (Researchgate, Academia.edu, etc.), published articles, various journals scientific papers, relevant specialized books in the field of reference, legislation, analysis and studies, official documents of the various fiscal bodies, fiscal documents and the interactive database of the European Commission, other relevant sources identified in libraries: Romanian Academy with related institutes, National Library, National Institute of Statistics, National Institute of Economic Research, etc. Also in the methodology we will analyze the studies carried out at European level following the surveys carried out among the respondents of the Member States, using the comparative, analytical, descriptive method, non-participatory and participatory observation, use of a set of information sources, collection of existing data at European level. The paper is also based on annual reports, publications, consolidated statistics provided by the European Commission, OECD, published annually, data that have been processed to provide an overview and analysis of the most important changes taking place in Europe as a whole but especially with the specialized literature on mountain economics, so specific for understanding the phenomena studied, and especially in Romania.

In our paper, we try to answer, through empirical research, a direct question about who Victor Slavescu was and how he became involved in supporting land loans between 1920 and 1944.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Another paper that shows us both the way of thinking economic, but especially the way of his involvement in the issues of the national economy (Slavescu, 1934), as Minister of Finance, and that in the spring of 1934, this report was presented to foreign experts, describing Romania's economic situation and assessing its ability to pay, as well as the specific elements of the Romanian economic and financial crisis respectively, the fact that the branches of the Romanian economy most affected by falling prices were: the production of cereals (in the autumn of 1929) and that of export raw materials (wood and oil in the spring of 1930). This crisis has led to a corresponding reduction in the value of production and the income of enterprises. Agriculture and the exploitation of wood and oil, constituting the main economic occupations of the Romanian population, resulted from this a general reduction of the purchasing power of the country in that period. Given that the fall in industrial and import prices was much less pronounced than that of agricultural products and export raw materials, the reduction in the purchasing power of the population led to an appropriate automatic compression of imports and manufactured output, All this has led to a decline in the profitability of industrial and commercial enterprises since the late

1930s' added to the insolvency of agriculture, added to some economic and financial policy measures and the withdrawal of foreign capital, since the autumn of 1929 and aggravated in 1931 by the banking crisis in Central Europe, caused a credit crisis and a crisis of public finances (1931), which was very much felt at that time. This crisis was characterized by the massive withdrawal of bank deposits, the collapse of stock prices and fixed income and the reduction of budget revenues continued until 1932 (Madgearu, 1933).

Moreover, it is noteworthy that in the paper published in 1925 (Slavescu, 1931:1), periods are mentioned regarding the appearance of the first land loans based on the principle of association.

Thus, in the period 1873–1975, after an extremely difficult period from all points of view, the rural and urban owners manage to form the first institutions dedicated to land loans, based on their associations and on the principle of joint and several liability of borrowers. Among those at the forefront of those who fought for the national organization of these credit institutions, meant to save rural and urban property from ruin and foreign seizure, we can mention personalities such as Ion Ghica, Ion C. Brătianu, Vasile Boerescu, D.A. Sturza, Gh. C. Cantacuzino, then Pană Buescu and Al. G. Băicolanu. They managed to organize the Rural Land Credit Institution in 1973 and the Urban Land Credit Institution in 1875, two institutions that have gone down in history as representative credit organizations.

Also in the above mentioned work it is reported that in 1881, Ion C. Brătianu is the initiator of the establishment of the peasant agricultural credit organization, having as main purpose the establishment of well-known Agricultural Credit Houses, organized at the level of all county residences and constituted by capital participation. The state, the counties and the individuals, with the aim of coming to the aid of the peasants, through productive credits based on the pawn policy. It is noteworthy that Slavescu proposed in a series of monographic works, published in the last 10 years of that period, to study the structure of the credit organization in as much detail as possible, monitoring it from the first beginnings to the present day.

Through the author's daily work, being in constant contact with commercial banks, he first researched the issue, (Slavescu, 1915), (Slavescu, 1916) and (Slavescu, 1919) later completing them with two works of synthesis and general doctrine: (Slavescu, 1919:1), (Slavescu, 1920:1). And, by reuniting the territories in the Motherland, the credit organization acquires special values, as mentioned by the author, and having specific territorial elements, the author researching and highlighting first the activity of Romanian banks in Transylvania, led by the oldest institution in this country. Transylvania (Slavescu, 1919) and then two financial institutions from Bucovina (Slavescu, 1919) and (Slavescu, 1920) on various private financial institutions across the country. This study was later supplemented with

¹ Here is how the average value of agricultural production per hectare varied:

<i>Period</i>	<i>Average income (lei / ha)</i>	<i>Index (%)</i>
1929	6.670	100,00
1930	3.925	58,85
1931	3.135	47,00
1932	3.416	50,97

(after "La Capacite de Paiement et la dette publique de la Roumanie"; Memorandum presented by Mr. Virgil Madgearu, Minister of Finance, Bucharest, 1933).

The average income per hectare decreases, within two years, by 53%. Rural households could obtain, in 1931, only less than half of what they obtained for their products in 1929. For the goods that the rural household needed, prices did not fall to the same extent.

up-to-date data in two other studies on (Slavescu, 1924) and (Slavescu, 1923). After these detailed studies on the entire banking system in Romania as a whole, the country's financial institutions were investigated. In (Slavescu, 1924) which is now followed by the presence (Slavescu, 1924). The author aimed at the methodical, systematic and objective analysis of credit organizations, and especially of land credit in Romania between 1920 and 1944, based on a rich documentary material, commented and explained with the greatest objectivity, as appropriate in scientific papers.

The paper (Slavescu, 1925:213) mentions aspects that are found in our times and that reflect present realities, namely the fact that at that time compared to the shortcomings of those times, Slavescu stressed that all those involved at that time were obliged to learn from those achieved and to achieve a high-performing economy with high productivity, respectively to re-implement tools for both private and public wealth support, and (Slavescu, 1925:315) are mentioned the three categories of loans granted to the market at that time were in the form discount and Lombard for trade and industry and through pawnshops for farmers, which experienced a continuous development between 1919 and 1920, and an increase in the year of monetary unification, when through this operation it reduced a large amount of money, which mediate business transactions so that the need for credit becomes more and more deeply felt in that period. The year 1921 is also the date when the National Bank begins to work directly in the new provinces, through the direct branches it set up on the occasion of monetary unification. The author researches the action of the National Bank in relation to the economic market for the last period, and mentions that it is interesting to follow the development taken in terms of financial, industrial and commercial enterprises across the country by the General Directorate of Statistics of the Ministry of Industry and Trade.

In order to have a clear picture of the development of these enterprises, in terms of the number of units and the share capital, for the whole country, we present in the table below their presentation.

Table 1. Presentation of the number of units and share capital, for the whole country in the reference years 1910, 1920, 1921 and 1922

Institutions	1910		1920	
	No.	Capital	No.	Capital
Banks	486	711,264,038	542	1,966,663,899
Industrial companies	321	1,007,077,108	447	2,767,128,718
Commercial companies	10	132,081,494	146	336,767,680
Other companies	22	131,660,736	19	97,682,590
Total	939	1,982,084,376	1,154	5,168,242,889
Institutions	1921		1922	
	No.	Capital	No.	Capital
Banks	556	2,406,400,470	683	3,334,767,780
Industrial companies	529	5,106,690,849	720	7,549,070,670
Commercial companies	159	467,961,268	218	1,125,640,662
Other companies	22	114,376,675	29	152,548,524
Total	1.266	8,095,429,263	1,650	12,162,027,636

Source: History of the National Bank of Romania (1880–1924), Victor Slavescu, published in 1925, page 329

Table 2. Presentation of banks' participation quotas (%) in the years 1920, 1921, 1922 and 1923

Banking institution	1920	1921	1922	1923
Marmorosch, Blak&Co Bank	30.80	19.42	25.52	21.21
Banca de Credit Român	12.30	13.01	11.84	10.78
Banca Comercială Română	11.80	13.22	11.32	11.19
Banca Românească	14.50	14.46	10.41	8.40
Banca Comercială Italiană și Română	2.20	12.30	6.98	9.35
Banque Belge pour l'Etranger	-	3.85	6.81	12.11
Banca Chrissoveloni	2.70	2.88	5.45	7.25
Bank of Roumania Ltd.	5.70	4.60	4.94	4.70
Banca Generală a Țării Românești	4.00	5.29	3.68	2.30
Banca Națională a României	6.91	4.02	3.61	3.15
Dresdner Bank	-	-	3.41	3.67
Banca L. Berkovitz	2.10	2.52	2.00	2.99
Banca Cerealiștilor	-	-	1.48	0.59
Banca Agricolă	2.30	1.69	0.84	0.64
Banca de Scont a României	3.50	1.68	0.83	0.94
Banca Franco-Română	0.85	1.05	0.63	0.58
Banca Țărănească	0.25	0.09	0.20	0.08
Banca Sindicatului Agricol Ialomița	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02
Banca Sindicatului Agricol Ilfov	0.04	0.05	0.02	0.01
Banca Viticolă a României	0.02	-	0.01	0.01

Source: History of the National Bank of Romania (1880–1924), Victor Slavescu, published in 1925, p. 329

Victor Slavescu's determination and dedication to supporting the development of the national economy, namely the agricultural cooperative and agricultural credit, is also evidenced by the fact that he firmly believed that in a country where almost two-thirds of all cultivated land belongs to peasants and where they make up almost 80 percent of the total population, the problem of popular agricultural credit is not only a matter of humanitarianism, but a vast economic and social problem, the solution of which depends on the lifting of the state on the unshakable foundations (Slavescu, 1925:322).

Moreover, Slavescu stated that we need first of all a strong and important agrarian cooperation with all branches of activity. When 80 percent of the country's population lives in the country and its main occupation is agriculture, when the agrarian reform goes from the phase of its legal application to enter the phase of its agricultural technical organization, there is no doubt that there is constant concern that must be educating and guiding the peasant towards a better culture to be achieved only through agricultural cooperation (Slavescu, 1928:1). However, Victor Slavescu drew attention to the costs of financing, given that interest rates represented between 20 and 60 percent of the value of loans. He feared that it could lead to the ruin of the peasant household, the basis of the national economy, and ruling for the regulation of interest rates by the National Bank of Romania (Slavescu, 1928:1).

Victor Slavescu campaigned for the adoption of a code of cooperation that would provide the legal framework for the cooperative movement, considering the cooperation a

moral movement based on the solidarity of *many and weak*, meant to improve their material and moral condition. The code of cooperation was to operate on the principle that self-financing underlies the whole movement, either in the form of share capital or in the form of interest-bearing deposits from associate members. It was necessary to show solidarity with all financial forces belonging to the associate members. There were two principles on which the organization of a modern co-operative movement was based, namely the unit of financing and the organization by categories of financing. According to the first principle, the task of providing credit for the entire co-operative movement rested only with the people's banks, the federal people's banks and the Central People's Banks. Victor Slavescu considered that the financing unit will ensure a more equitable distribution of funds in the entire body of the cooperation. The organization on different categories of financing was necessary to cover the real needs of the peasants and the working mass, this being an absolute priority at that time, but which we consider to be fully valid even in the current times (Slavescu, 1928).

After the voting process (Slavescu, 1928) regarding the realization of these cooperatives, he defined the cooperation as not an association of capitals, but an integration of souls, a group of people who, before bringing their modest good, bring their work together what can they have better in their souls. In 1936 he published an article suggestively entitled *I believe in cooperation*, in which he stated that only in this way could a very good peasant household be organized.

Analyzing the situation of the national economy, Professor Slavescu came to the conclusion that it confronted two currents: the current healthy, Romanian, based on the logical doctrine of perfecting general interests and the current nuanced by international finance, which through its instruments and unfortunately with the collaboration of a few lost people he sought to make the idea of selfish gain, of the moment, materialized in the form of the game and the stock exchanges, triumph (Slavescu, 1920).

The Romanian state had several models at its disposal that it could follow in terms of capital, but Victor Slavescu spoke for the example of Great Britain, which had introduced shares of one-pound sterling in order to give anyone the opportunity to participate in large economic and financial enterprises. The American example of the Rockefellers, in which capital was concentrated in the hands of a few people, was considered dangerous because it could lead to financial dictatorship. What was happening in the Soviet Union could not be a solution for the Romanian economy because in this state the contemporaries were witnessing a real tension that could lead to the destruction of the economic organism without putting anything in return (Slavescu, 1920).

Victor Slavescu (Slavescu, 1919) stressed that any foreign investment has a well-defined purpose, because no state contributes to the economic rise of another state, constantly campaigning for the defense of national interests. From Slavescu's point of view, the liberals wanted the collaboration between the foreign and the domestic capital, in which the Romanian capital would be the majority. This combative attitude was characteristic of the years immediately following the First World War and, in addition to a psychological explanation, it had its causes in the many difficult situations that the ruling circles in Bucharest faced during the peace treaty negotiations. Victor Slavescu even stated that international finance fuels certain political currents that are against Romania and that exert foreign exchange pressures in order to obtain political and economic concessions that no independent and sovereign state can admit (Slavescu, 1919)

The relationship between financial circles and political parties has preoccupied Victor Slavescu since the early 1920s, given that liberals were involved in many of the most important national banking institutions. Immediately after the First World War, the National Liberal Party was intensely attacked in this direction and that is why Victor Slavescu felt obliged to offer an explanation. There was talk of the existence of so-called political banks, those banks in which part of the capital was owned by politically involved figures. The main accusation was that the national finances, mostly liberal, were in the tow of political parties and, in most cases, acted to the detriment of the general interests. Victor Slavescu responded to these accusations by explaining that a credit institution that would recruit its means of work only from among political partisans was practically an aberration. The accusers were trying to prove that the most appropriate solution for Romania was massive collaboration with foreign capital, because international finance was independent of domestic political life. Victor Slavescu also dismantled the argument that national finance is not political as long as its capital is in the form of bearer shares. The involvement of many politicians in financial activities was explained by Slavescu by the lack of personalities.

A complex personality, Victor Slavescu was and will remain an intellectual activist, promoter of the cooperative form of association and rural financing (agricultural credit), and who left us a national wealth that can be capitalized by both present generations and of future generations (Isarescu, 2001).

CONCLUSION

Current challenges often influence our decision and our way of thinking. However, I appreciate that reflecting carefully on everything that has been well-founded and achieved in the past by the personalities of the moment (as is Victor Slavescu), determines us economists to approach models of financing the mountainous rural area starting from these models that were made between 1891–1977.

Fig. 1. Entrepreneur Microfinance Model (MIT)***

*** The Microfinance Entrepreneur (MIT) – model concept developed in my doctoral thesis “MICROFINANCING. CONCEPTS AND APPLICATIONS IN THE RURAL ENVIRONMENT ” October, 2017.

Agenda:

MIT – Entrepreneur Microfinance Model (MIT)

MSM – Micro-enterprise specialized in microfinance (Network of 1580 MSM)

Beneficiaries of microfinance products:

MAR – small entrepreneurs from rural areas;

FSZ – semi-subsistence agricultural farms;

TA – young entrepreneurs;

PEF – Financially excluded people (poor)

Funders:

FT – traditional financiers (banks, NFIs, international financial institutions, etc.)

FI – investment funds;

DG – government donors (Government, Government Agencies, etc.) especially in the case of programs to stimulate the crediting of the population through social credit with ZERO interest and major impact, on financial support, financial education, social integration, business taxation and sustainability at the level of rural environment.

GNI – non-governmental donors (international and national associations, foundations, e.g.)

Romania is a country where more than 50% of the territory and population is outside the urban. It is the country where the rural civilization with everything related to it has been amazingly preserved. The natural setting and the way of "country life" are the closest to the traditional image that could be preserved in Western Europe. In addition, rural communities, although seemingly out of history, are alive. Moreover, the village, regardless of the geographical space in which it is located, is the expression of man's connection with nature. These are the reasons why our country has great potential for the development of the mountain economy in rural areas (including current financial technologies in the microfinance model and the development of rural entrepreneurship), and its practice is absolutely necessary at this stage.

The existing legislative framework (Law 197, 2018) provides concrete solutions to support mountain areas, and we can mention a few of them, namely:

- (1) This law approves the Program to encourage activities in the mountain area, for which 1 billion euros are allocated for a period of 10 years from the entry into force of this law, from the state budget, through the budget of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.
- (2) The program to encourage activities in the mountain area is a source of support for performance in the agricultural and non-agricultural sector.) Allows us to achieve a mountainous and sustainable economy.

The tools, mechanisms and funding solutions for researchers must be closely linked to the objective of this Program to encourage activities in the mountain area provided for in the above-mentioned Law, and the Microfinance Entrepreneur Model (MIT) may be one of these tools, but using all the past work of great personalities, the model can be successful by anchoring in the reality of the present, using past work and looking to the future.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Isărescu Mugur, Surica Rosentuler, Wilhelm Salater, Slăvoiu Ovidiu și Marițiu Sabina,** 2001, *The Life and Work of Victor Slavescu*, National Bank of Romania, Restituio nr.1, ISSN 1582–7550;
- Madgearu M. Virgil,** 1933, *La Capacite de Paiement et la dette publique de la Roumanie; Memorandum presente par*, Ministre des Finances, Bucarest;
- Ristea and Franc,** 2013, *Methodology in scientific research*, Publishing house Expert, Bucarest, Romania;
- Scurtu Ioan,** 1996, *The history of Romania in the years 1918–1940. The evolution from the democratic regime to the dictatorship*, Bucharest, Didactic and Pedagogical Publishing House, p.12;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1907, *Chestiunea agrară în România/Die Agrarfrage in Rumänien*; PhD thesis;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1915, *Large Commercial Banks*, study published in the Archive for Science and Social Reform;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1916, *Medium Commercial Banks*, study published in the Archive for Science and Social Reform;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1919, *Working methods of international finance*, in “Viitorul”, year XII, no.3547, p.1
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1919, *Banking Movement in Old Romania, Banking Policy Issues in Romania*, study published in the Archive for Science and Social Reform;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1919, *Banca Albina from Sibiu*, study published in the Archive for Science and Social Reform;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1919, *Bucovina “Banca Țării”*, study published in the Archive for Science and Social Reform;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1919, *Romanian Finance and Foreign Capital*, published in the newspaper “Viitorul” on February 14, 1919;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1920, *Democratization of capitals*, in “Viitorul”, year XIII, no. 3634, p.1
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1920, *Casa de Economii din Bucovina*, study published in the Archive for Science and Social Reform;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1920, *Great Finance in Romania during the war*, study published in the Archive for Science and Social Reform;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1922, *Credit Organization of Romania*, study published in the Archive for Science and Social Reform;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1923, *Sasii Credit Organization from Transylvania*, published in the Bulletin of the Romanian Economic Institute;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1924, *To the Great Romanian Banks of Transylvania*, published in the Archive for Science and Social Reform;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1924, *Financial Loans in Romania*, published in the Bulletin of the Romanian Economic Institute;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1924, *History of agricultural credit and people's banks*;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1924, *House of Deposits, Economy and Consignments*;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1924, *National Industrial Credit Company*;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1925, *History of the National Bank of Romania (1880–1924)*, p.213, p. 329, p. 322, p.315;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1928, *New orientations in cooperation*, in “Viitorul”, year XXI, no.6182 /, p.1;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1928, *The problem of interest*, in “Democracy”, year XV, no. 4, p.65;
- Slăvescu Victor,** 1928, *Financing the cooperation*, in “Viitorul”, year XX, no. 6013, p.1;

Slăvescu Victor, 1928, *Cooperation Code*;

Slăvescu Victor, 1931, *The history and development of popular banks*, in the Bulletin of the Romanian Economic Institute, year IV, "no.3 / 1925, p. 213", p.1;

Slăvescu Victor, 1934, *The problems of a directed economy in Romania*;

National Bank of Romania (BNR), 2001, *Restitutio, Viața și opera lui Victor Slăvescu*, ediția nr.1;

Law no. 197 of July 20, 2018 of the mountain – *The program to encourage activities in the mountain area*, ART. 16.